

Research

Investigation of rheological behavior of a debris flow: a case study in the Longchi area, Sichuan province, China

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Abstract: Debris flow is a devastating natural hazard phenomenon in mountainous areas, which causes human losses and damage to infrastructures. The main triggering factors for debris flow are rainfall and earthquake. The 2008 Wenchuan earthquake, followed by heavy rain on August 13th, 2010, which initiated a series of debris flow, resulted in considerable loss of lives and infrastructure. Therefore, it is pertinent to investigate characteristics of debris flow based on the behavior of rheological parameters. The main objective of this research is to evaluate the rheological behavior of debris flow. The main characteristics and dimensions of current debris flows have been investigated by fieldwork. Soil samples from the riverbed and sources area were collected for extensive laboratory testing. A series of laboratory testing, which includes soil indices test and rheological parameters of debris flow containing granular materials with size finer than 0.075mm have been obtained using a rotational rheometer (Physica MCR). The rheological behavior has been examined at different ranges of volumetric concentration. These results showed the values of shear stress had been proportionally increasing with the increase of solid volumetric concentration. Based on the "8.13" debris flow characteristics in the Longchi area, these resulted rheological parameters of debris flow can be used to obtain the features of other debris flows in this area.

Keywords: Debris Flow, Longchi area, Rheology

1. Introduction

Debris flow is a kind of solid-liquid two-phase fluid containing a large number of mud, sand, and boulders. Debris flow occurs when poorly sorted sediment turns out to be saturated with water and moves down the slopes due to gravity (Iverson, 1997). It usually occurs in areas with complex geological structures, where faults and folds are well developed, especially in mountainous regions with high seismic activity. In the process of movement and deposition, it directly or indirectly damages the environmental system through erosion, impact, siltation, and river blocking. Debris flow disasters are more common in the mountain environment (Iverson, 1997).

Wenchuan earthquake induced a large number of landslides, most of the deposits remained in the slope and gully, forming a large number of loose material for sources of debris flow. Under the action of later heavy rainfall, a large number of landslides occurred, and the source of loose solid materials in the seismic region increased further (Chen et al., 2012; Lin et al., 2004; Tang et al., 2012; Tang et al., 2011; Tang et al., 2009). Studies have shown that the impact of earthquakes on debris flow disasters may be as long as 30 years (Xie et al., 2009) of which 5-10 years after the earthquake is the high occurrence period of debris flow (Tang et al., 2011).

On August 13, 2010, the Longchi area of Dujiangyan City, Sichuan Province, suffered heavy rainfall. The occurrence of debris flow at many places along the Longxi river caused most of the houses along the river to be destroyed, damaged the roads, bridges and other transportation facilities in the Longchi scenic spot, resulting in economic losses of more than 550 million yuan (Yu et al., 2011). The "5.12" earthquake caused the reduction in the stability of a large number of mountains in the Southwestern earthquake area, and the mountain structure became more fragile. A large number of landslides occurred on both sides of the mountain valley after the earthquake, and the loose deposits produced by the landslides remained at the bottom of the slopes on both sides, which increased the source reserves of debris flows, leading to the recognizable increase of debris flow frequency and the further increase of the risk range in a period of time after the earthquake. The earthquake accelerated the development of geological disasters. After the earthquake, debris flow disasters will continue to be active for a while, and the frequency

and scale of debris flow disasters will increase significantly (Cui et al., 2010) compared with that before the earthquake. After the earthquake, some new houses in Longchi town of Dujiangyan City were located in the debris flow gully area, which was seriously damaged in the debris flow disaster of August 13, 2010.

Keeping in view of above mentioned issues, this paper focuses on the rheological parameters of debris flow and the impact of the solid volumetric concentration C_v on the rheology of a fine mixture of debris flow material.

2. Study area

The study was conducted in the Longchi watershed, located within 20 km from the epicenter of the 2008 Wenchuan earthquake in Sichuan province of China. The study area is placed between 31°01'41.53" N and 103°30'04.38" E to 31°10'47.42" N and 103°35'26.42" E, as shown in **Figure 1**. The area of the basin is about 78.1 km², and the elevation ranges from 774m to 3229m. The slope varies from 0 to 80°, and the average channel gradient of debris flows is >30.63°.

Figure 1: Overview map showing the location of the study area (Longchi basin)

2.1. Climatology

Statistical analysis of temperature and rainfall data in Longchi area of Dujiangyan City for more than 50 years since 1955 represent that the highest temperature is 35 °C, the lowest temperature is -4.1 °C, the average annual temperature is 12.2 °C, and the average yearly precipitation is 1134.8mm (Yu et al., 2011). Due to the influence of the atmospheric environment and the surface environment, the rainfall is inconsistent in area, and the intensity of each precipitation is diverse. The hourly and daily rainfall intensity during the flood season is often tremendous.

Rainfall intensity is the main factor inducing geological disasters. Meanwhile August 4, 2010, there has been rainfall in the Longchi area, and the water content of loose soil and landslide deposits on the surface of the mountain has gradually turn out to be saturated. Rainfall suddenly increased at 16:00 on August 13, 2010, and the hourly rainfall from 16:00 to 17:00 reached 75mm (20 years return period), as shown in **Figure 2**; the maximum 2-hour rainfall reached 128.3mm. ; Rainfall reaches 150mm for three consecutive hours. The cumulative rainfall in the 17 hours from 14:00 on August 13 to 7:00 on August 14 reached 229mm (Chang et al., 2017). This rainfall process directly induced debris flows along the Longxi river in Longchi, among which many debris flow gullies deposits such as Jianping gully, Zhuacao gully, and Shuijiuping gully blocked the river.

Figure 2: Precipitation graphs of the 8.13 rainstorm event in the study area.

2.2.Topography

The topography of Longchi area belongs to the stepped distribution of middle and low mountains and river valleys (Yu et al., 2011). The highest elevation is at the top of Longchigang mountain (about 3060m), and the lowest elevation is at the water surface of Zipingpu Reservoir (about 760m), with a relative elevation difference of 2300m. Mountainous area (3060m-1000m above sea level) is distributed in the watershed under the selected study area of Longchi gully. The low mountain and valley plain area (1000m-760m lower than the sea level) is distributed in the basin below the study area.

2.3.Geology

The area where Longchi town is located is the middle-south section of the Longmenshan structural belt in the geological structure system, which belongs to the Huaxia tectonic system. It is mainly situated on the Northwest side of Yingxiu-Beichuan fault. The Yingxiu-Beichuan fault was ruptured during the 2008 Wenchuan earthquake. The occurrence of rock formations in the Longchi area has changed dramatically, the rock formations are highly weathered, and rock fractures are well developed.

The exposed strata in the study area are mainly the Proterozoic, Sinian, Triassic, and Quaternary. It is mostly composed of andesite, granite, tuff, diorite, and a small number of metamorphic rocks. The surface layer is the Quaternary eluvium, colluvium, and diluvium (Yongping and Chuan, 2014; Yu et al., 2011).

3. Materials and methods

3.1.Field investigation

The field investigation has been done to determine the dynamic characteristics of the debris flow. Fieldwork was conducted in January 2019 to confirm the visual interpretation. **Figure 3 (a)** showing the hotel beside the Longxi river was struck caused by the Aug 13, 2010 debris flow. Soil samples of debris flow were collected, as shown in **Figure 3 (b)** and **(c)**. The average deposit thickness was measured using a laser range finder. Measurement of other parameters includes a cross-section of the channel, slope of the channel, and hydraulic radius of the channel at various sections along the channel to the depositional

fan. Different sources of debris flow have been observed, such as channel bed erosion and shallow landslides is shown in *Figure 4*.

Figure 3: (a) Hotel beside the Longxi river was struck caused by the Aug 13, 2010 debris flow (b) Collection of samples from source area (c) A Series of debris flow deposition.

Figure 4: Parameters measured in the debris-flow catchments.

The depositional fan of the Longchi gully was located at the river bank. The frontal part of the debris flow marched into the Minjiang River, and part of it was washed away. The deposition fan pushed the river course to the opposite side. The slope angle at the mouth of Gully is relatively small; hence a considerable amount of the debris stopped there and posed the possibility of future debris flows.

3.2.Laboratory analysis of soil

3.2.1. Grain-size analysis

To evaluate the rheological parameter used to identify the debris flow activity, initially, sieve analysis is required and, after that, the rheological ones. The materials tested have been collected from different zones of debris flow. After the collection of samples, each sample was prepared for the sieve analysis. Firstly, large samples should be segregated through a sample splitter, which ensures that each sample represents the entire sample. This amount has been optimized according to the vertical sieve characteristics. The following sieves were used: 60mm, 20mm, 10mm, 5mm, 2mm, 1mm, 0.5mm, 0.25mm and 0.075mm. The laser diffraction method used a representative sample of the relatively small portion passed through the 0.075 mm sieve with the Mastersizer 2000S instrument, as shown in *Figure 5*.

Figure 5: Sieve analysis instrument (Left). Laser diffraction for particle size distribution (Right).

The resulting data of sand and silt utilizing laser diffraction analysis is in the form of volume percent. This data of volume percent have been converted into weight percent and merged with data acquired by sieve analysis to obtain the final grain-size curves. The shape

of the grain-size distribution curves is shown in **Figure 6**. The shapes of curves represent that the soil is well-graded gravely sandy silt with a small fraction of clay.

Figure 6: Particle-size distribution curves of soil samples

3.2.2. Rheological analysis

Apparatus and background

The rotational Rheometer (Physica MCR) prepared with parallel plates geometry systems to maintain the accuracy and to lower the risk of miscalculation of rheometrical measurements, as shown in **Figure 7**. The design of the parallel plate comprises a lower plate (fixed) and an upper plate (rotational) with a diameter of 4 mm. The gap in the middle of two plates should be ten times the diameter of maximum grain size, d_{max} (Chhabra and Richardson, 1999). The distance in the middle of plates has been fixed on the basis of the maximum diameter of grain size due to different particle size are distributed in the material. The shear rate and the shear stress are calculated with the following equations:

$$\dot{\gamma}_R = \dot{\gamma}(R) = \frac{\Omega \cdot R}{H} \quad 1$$

$$\tau(\dot{\gamma}_R) = \frac{3T}{2\pi R^3} + \frac{\dot{\gamma}_R}{2\pi R^3} * \frac{dT}{d\dot{\gamma}_R} \quad 2$$

In Eq. (1) and (2), R is the upper plate radius, H is the gap, Ω is the rotation velocity (rad/s), and T is the torque (Coussot, 1997).

Figure 7: The rotational Rheometer (Physica MCR) equipped with parallel plates geometry systems

Test procedure

In the mode of controlled-rate, the mixture of debris flow has been analyzed, and the temperature of the entire process was constant (20 ± 0.5 °C). The analyzed debris flow mixtures have been tested in rate-controlled mode at a constant temperature (20 ± 0.5 °C). The following shear rate levels from 0 to 100 1/s have been applied to obtain the flow curves of shear stress and shear rate. Each test was repeated at least three times to ensure the accuracy of the experiment results, and the average results were considered. The flow curves of granular materials with sizes below 0.075 mm have been obtained from the geometry configurations of the used rheometer. The tests were performed based on different water content mixtures. Solid volumetric concentration (C_v) refers to the ratio of the volume of solid matter in the fluid to the total volume of the fluid that has been considered. The solid volumetric concentration C_v , i.e., the ratio of the amount of solids to the total mixture, has been considered. The total solid volumetric concentration C_v is defined as:

$$C_v = \frac{V_s}{V_s + V_w} \quad 3$$

In Eq. (3), v_w , and v_s are, respectively, the volumes of water and solid in the sample. In order to consider a significant range of the sediment concentration for the material tested, mixtures with C_v changing from 40% to 50% have been prepared.

4. Results and discussion

The flow curves for the two analyzed materials have been reported in *Figure 8* and *Figure 9*. It is found that all mixtures of the studied debris flow act as a non-Newtonian fluid, particularly, similar to yield stress fluids: Shear stress rises due to rise in shear rate and the value of shear stress increases non-linearly at a point of yield stress, which reflects the shear stress value required to start the flow.

Figure 8: (a) Viscosity and (b) Shear stress versus shear rate for tests of sample-1 with different volumetric concentration C_v . The Bingham model fitted to the data.

Figure 9: (a) Viscosity and (b) Shear stress versus shear rate for tests of sample-2 with different volumetric concentration C_v . The Bingham model fitted to the data.

The impact of the solid volumetric concentration C_v on the rheology of fine debris flow material mixtures has been analyzed. It is found that the values of shear stress have been proportionally increased with the increase of solid volumetric concentration. Moreover, at equal solid volumetric concentration, the shear stresses of Sample-1 are higher than Sample-2 due to different particle nature.

Figure 10: Yield stress τ_y versus solid volumetric concentration C_v .

Figure 11: Bingham viscosity versus volumetric concentration C_v

It is noted that Bingham generalized is the best model for experimental data. The solid volumetric concentration C_v and obtained yield stress τ_y is graphically represented in **Figure 10**. While obtained Bingham viscosity and the solid volumetric concentration C_v is graphically represented in **Figure 11**. Several researchers (Coussot et al., 1998; Coussot and Piau, 1994; Kaitna et al., 2007; Major and Pierson, 1992; O'Brien and Julien, 1988; O'Brien and Julien, 1985; Phillips and Davies, 1991), presented the relation between the yield stress and solid volumetric concentration and following formula can be used as mentioned in Eq. (4) and (5).

$$\mu_B = \alpha_1 e^{\beta_1 C_v} \quad 4$$

$$\tau_B = \alpha_2 e^{\beta_2 C_v} \quad 5$$

Where C_v is the volumetric concentration and α_1 , β_1 , α_2 and β_2 are empirical coefficients defined by laboratory experiments and their values are shown in **Table 1**.

According to previous studies (Coussot and Piau, 1994; Kaitna et al., 2007; Schatzmann, 2005), the rheological properties changes due to concentrations of larger particles utilizing the nonconventional rheometers. It can be noted that as the solid volumetric concentration C_v in the mixture increases, the yield stress τ_y and Bingham viscosity increases exponentially (Dai et al., 1980; Hübl and Steinwendtner, 2001; O'Brien and Julien, 1988).

Table 1: Rheological parameters obtained from the regression of experimental results

Rheological Parameters		Sample-1	Sample-2
Bingham Yield stress τ_y (Pa)	α_2	0.0019	5E-05
	β_2	22.76	28.59
Bingham dynamic viscosity μ_B (Pa s)	α_1	1E-06	3E-07
	β_1	26.76	29.67

Such findings indicate that a slight change of the solid proportion induced in the field by rainfalls contributes to a small reduction in the yield stress and a flow that achieves shear rate higher than that associated with a rapid flow of critical shear rate. Formerly, the movement of the fluid will cease at the place of a gentle slope. The yield stress is among

the crucial factors in the estimation of hazardous regions by way of computational simulations because it influences the deposition area's magnitude and stability and can differ across a wide variety of values. Therefore, the rheological parameters calculated by the conventional rheometer only considers the limited size of grains and does not characterize the natural phenomena.

5. Conclusions

The "8 · 13" debris flow in Longchi area caused significant losses to the lives and property of residents. Among which Shuijiuping gully and other debris flow caused considerable damage to the residential houses and roads at the gully mouth. Because of the substantial loss, these debris flow gullies are still in an active stage, and there are a vast number of loose debris sources that can initiate the debris flow in the Longchi area. In this study, rheological parameters of debris flow containing granular materials with sizes below 0.075 mm have been obtained. The tests were performed based on different water content and sediment concentration. The impact of the solid volumetric concentration C_v on the rheology of a fine mixture of debris flow material has been analyzed. It is found that the values of shear stress have been proportionally increased with the increase of solid volumetric concentration, and the mixture of debris flow acts as a non-Newtonian fluid.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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